

“NISBAT VA PROPORSIYA” BOBINI O‘QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISH

Xasanova Mukammalxon Bahodir qizi

**Farg‘ona viloyati Buvayda tumani 15-umumiy o‘rta ta‘lim maktabi
“Matematika” fani o‘qituvchisi**

E-mail: xasanovamukammalxon@gmail.com

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Mamlakatimizda ta‘lim tizimining modernizatsiya qilinishi, uni tarkibiy jihatdan qayta qurish, ta‘lim, fan, texnika va texnologiyaning iqtisodiyot va madaniyatning jahon miqyosidagi zamonaviy yutuqlarini hisobga olgan holda o‘qitish jarayoniga innovatsiyalarni tatbiq etish bilan bir qatorda, ta‘lim-tarbiya jarayoni ishtirokchilarining imkoniyatlari va ehtiyojlari nuqtai nazaridan ular uchun zarur va etarli shart-sharoitlarni yaratib berishni bugungi kun talab etmoqda. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020 yil 7-maydagi “Matematika sohasidagi ta‘lim sifatini oshirish va ilmiy tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish choratadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-4708-sonli Qarorining qabul qilinishi fikrimizning yaqqol isbotidir. Qarorda Matematika fani o‘quv-metodik dasturi mazmun va mohiyatini sohalarga moslashtirish, matematika fani bo‘yicha o‘quv adabiyotlari (darsliklar)ni turli dasturlar va umumiy metodologik asosda hamda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari vositalari yordamida tushuntiruvchi real misollar, grafik materiallar asosida tayyorlash hamda matematik ta‘limda fanlararo integratsiyani ta‘minlash masalalari ham asosiy ustuvor yo‘nalishlardan biri etib belgilangan. O‘quv qo‘llanmada matematik ta‘limning maqsadi, mazmuni, metodlari va uning vositalarini matematika darslariga tatbiq qilish qonuniyatlari psixologik, pedagogik va didaktik nuqtayi nazardan bayon qilingan. Chunki, matematika o‘qitish metodikasi kursi asosiy mutaxassislik fanlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Bu kursda matematikaning rivojlanish tarixi va matematika o‘qitishdagi umumiy va xususiy metodlari o‘rganiladi. Matematika o‘qitish metodikasi pedagogika, psixologiya, algebra, matematik tahlil, analitik geometriya va oddiy differensial tenglamalar fanlari bilan chambarchas bog‘liqdir. O‘quv qo‘llanma fan dasturi doirasida olingan nazariy bilimlar va ko‘nikmalar, oliy va o‘rta maxsus o‘quv yurtlarida (litsey, kollej), umumta‘lim maktablarida matematika fanini zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida o‘qitishda va fan tarixini o‘rganishda keng qo‘llanilishi nazarda tutilgan. 6 O‘quvchilarga fanning ba‘zi mavzular bo‘yicha darslari elektron vositalar yordamida tashkil etilishi, o‘quvchilarning fanni o‘zlashtirishlari uchun o‘qitishning ilg‘or va zamonaviy usullaridan foydalanish, yangi axborotlipedagogik texnologiyalarni tatbiq etish, ushbu fanni o‘zlashtirishda darslik, o‘quv va metodik qo‘llanmalar, ma‘ruza matnlari, tarqatma materiallar, virtual stendlardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ma‘ruza va seminar mashg‘ulot darslarida mos ravishdagi ilg‘or pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalaniladi. Bu borada zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarining aqliy hujum, munozarali dars va boshqa usullaridan foydalanish ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan.

Matematik ta‘lim – o‘quvchilar tomonidan matematik bilimlar tizimining egallanishi, bilish uquvi va ko‘nikma asosida o‘z dunyoqarashini shakllantirilishi, shaxsning axloqiy va boshqa sifatlarini, ijodiy kuch va boshqa imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirishga ko‘maklashuvchi jarayon va u beradigan natijadir. Ta‘lim ikki aspektda ko‘rib chiqiladi: –ijtimoiy (jamiyatning ta‘limga talabini aks ettiradigan); –shaxsiy (har bir shaxsga mo‘ljallangan maqsadni belgilaydigan). Ma‘lumotli shaxsda quyidagi xususiyatlar mavjud bo‘ladi: aniqlik; fikrning keng va

egiluvchanligi; muammolarning keng doirasida mo'ljallanish va ularni yyechishga intilish; ehtiyojning xilma-xilligi; voqealar rivojlanishini bashorat qila bilish va o'z faoliyatini modellashtira olish; yuqori ishchanlik. Matematik ta'limning asosiy maqsadi, o'quvchilarda real hayotga matematik nuqtayi nazardan qaray bilish uquvini, matematika va ilovasining amaliy yo'nalishlarini ko'ra bilishni shakllantirishdan iborat bo'ladi.

Umuman, k va n noldan farqli sonlar bo'lsa, $k : n$ bo'linma nisbat, k va n sonlar esa nisbatning hadlari deyiladi.

$k : n = q$ yoki $k : n = (k \cdot p) : (n \cdot p)$ yoki $=$

Nisbat – birinchi son ikkinchi sondan necha marta katta ekanini yoki birinchi son ikkinchi sonning qanday qismini tashkil qilishini bildiradi.

Ikki nisbatning tengligi proporsiya deyiladi.

Demak, $=$ tenglik proporsiyadir. Uni $4 : 5 = 8 : 10$ deb yozsa ham bo'ladi. Bundan $4 \cdot 10 = 5 \cdot 8$, ya'ni $40 = 40$ tenglikni olamiz. 5 va 8 sonlari proporsiyaning o'rta hadlari, 4 va 10 sonlari esa uning chetki hadlari deyiladi.

Umuman, $a : b = c : d$ proporsiya uchun $a \cdot d = b \cdot c$ tenglik o'rinli. Aksincha, a, b, c va d nolga teng bo'lmagan sonlar bo'lib, ular uchun $a \cdot d = b \cdot c$ tenglik o'rinli bo'lsa, bundan $=$ tenglik kelib chiqadi, ya'ni a, b, c va d sonlar proporsiyani tashkil qiladi.

Proporsiyaning asosiy xossasi: Proporsiyaning o'rta hadlari ko'paytmasi uning chetki hadlari ko'paytmasiga teng.

$a : b = c : d$ $a \cdot d = b \cdot c$

a va d proporsiyaning chetki hadlari, b va c proporsiyaning o'rta hadlari deyiladi.

1-misol.

$3 : 5 = 9 : 15$ proporsiyaning chetki hadlari 3 va 15, o'rta hadlari esa 5 va 9 dir. Chetki hadlari ko'paytmasi $3 \cdot 15 = 45$; o'rta hadlari ko'paytmasi $5 \cdot 9 = 45$; bundan, $45 = 45$, demak, proporsiyaning chetki hadlari ko'paytmasi uning o'rta hadlari ko'paytmasiga teng.

2-misol.

8,7,14,16 sonlari proporsiyani tashkil qiladimi?

Yechish: $7 \cdot 16 = 8 \cdot 14$ bo'lgani uchun berilgan sonlar proporsiya tashkil qiladi: $=$

3 – misol.

Proporsiyaning noma'lum hadini toping: $=$

Yechish: $3X = 6 \cdot 2$, $3X = 12$, $X = 4$

Proporsiyaning nom'lum hadini topish, odatda, proporsiyani yechish deyiladi.

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